

The Role of Generative AI in SPOC-Making: Student Perception of Partially AI-Generated Learning Resources

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Abstract. Since the introduction and rapid adoption of transformer-based generative Artificial Intelligence (Generative AI) technologies in 2022, such as ChatGPT, course creators have increasingly integrated these tools into learning design and MOOC-making (Massive Open Online Courses). Generative AI is argued to enhance the efficiency of MOOC-making, a time-consuming process. Responding to these shifts, this preliminary study investigates how a team of teacher educators employed generative AI to support the making of two Small Private Online Courses (SPOCs) and how online students perceived and engaged with partially AI-generated learning materials. Generative AI was used to develop various resources such as course texts, introductory paragraphs, images, and digital tests, with instructors adapting and refining the AI outputs. Using a simple quantitative survey approach, the study examines students' evaluations of the quality, usability, and learning outcomes associated with these resources. The findings suggest that partially AI-generated textual resources are perceived as valuable. Digital tests are also considered useful, although students highlight the need for improved formative feedback mechanisms. In contrast, visual learning resources, such as images and videos, receive lower evaluations, indicating limitations in their ability to support learning. The study concludes that while generative AI can enhance the accessibility and quality of certain online learning materials and contribute to streamlining MOOC-making processes, its overall impact on the student learning experience remains moderate.

Keywords: GenAI, learning design, MOOC-making, SPOC.

1 Introduction

Since the introduction and widespread adoption of generative Artificial Intelligence (Generative AI) technologies in November 2022, learning designers across many educational contexts have increasingly started exploring and using the technology to make different types of learning resources that students can use in their learning, which also includes MOOC-making processes. However, in this context, the role and use of generative AI in Small Private Online Courses (SPOCs) remains underresearched.

Thus, this preliminary study investigates how a group of teacher educators adopted generative AI tools and used them to develop partially AI-generated learning resources to make two SPOCs, which focused on the digitalization of schools. The tools were used to create learning materials such as course text, introductory paragraphs, reading instructions, digital tests, and images. That said, the primary goal is to report on students' perceptions of the quality, usability, and impact of these resources on their learning experience. To achieve this, the study addresses the following research question (RQ): *How do students perceive the use of partially AI-generated learning resources in SPOCs?* The next section presents relevant research, followed by a discussion of methodology and data analysis. The final section discusses the study's findings and concludes with its implications.

2 Relevant research

Over the last decade, there has been a growth of research exploring the relationships between MOOC-making and learning design [1-4]. But with the broad availability of generative AI tools, the field has taken a new direction, as researchers have begun to explore the role of generative AI technologies in creating learning experiences. The new body of research is still in a very early phase and has an explicit focus on documenting early experiences, frameworks, and challenges [5-12]. A recurring overarching theme, however, is the explicit focus on *human-in-the-loop processes*. This concept refers to a type of *collaborative process* where humans actively participate and control the entire process in which generative AI contributes to the development of learning content. Thus, the technology is rarely allowed to operate autonomously or freely determine learning content on its own. On the contrary, educators must actively engage with what the technology produces, critically assess its outputs, and ensure that the content aligns with pedagogical goals. This means that humans still retain full and ultimate responsibility for key elements of the learning design work.

This theme is expressed in various ways across the research contributions, primarily through the establishment of different perspectives aimed at clarifying the challenges involved. Conceptually, researchers have developed new frameworks to systematically integrate generative AI into course production. One such initiative is the GAIDE framework [8], which presents structured steps for how to work with learning objectives, how to draft content during the production phase, and how to refine and finalize learning materials through macro- and micro-level approaches. The model also advocates for iterative feedback loops during the course production process. When tested, the GAIDE framework demonstrated that the time spent producing courses could be drastically reduced without compromising content quality. Other conceptual studies call for broader reflections on the potential consequences of integrating generative AI into higher education. Some researchers [12] have coined the term the “sand heap paradox”, which highlight the question of where to draw the line between acceptable and unacceptable academic practice when using AI. A key conclusion is the continued necessity of human involvement, underlining the importance of regulation and critical pedagogy to avoid the risk of teaching and learning becoming superficial.

There are also empirical studies exploring the use of generative AI in the production of learning content. Some studies [9] even suggest that by using tools such as ChatGPT, it is possible to create a complete university-level online course within a single day—a remarkable claim. Quality assurance in these cases is maintained through expert review and plagiarism detection systems, with researchers concluding that the resulting learning content can be of high originality and quality. These findings show the advantages of the technology but also highlight the need for vigilance to avoid technological dependency. In another study [7], AI-generated programming learning resources were compared to similar resources created by students in a university course. A blind review process revealed that AI-generated resources were rated as almost equivalent in quality to the student-produced resources. But, the AI-generated content tended to be more homogeneous, while student-created resources showed greater variability in length and depth. Further studies have explored the use of large language models to create tailored courses for specific target groups [10]. One core group of researchers compared AI-generated course content with traditionally developed content and found no statistically significant differences. This suggests that language models can effectively support content development at scale. Other studies have taken a more specific focus, investigating how generative AI can foster creative learning experiences [5]. One study tested the application of AI in project-based learning, concluding that the technology can enhance creativity, collaboration, and personalized learning experiences. Researchers have also emphasized the need for educators to develop new competencies such as the emerging AI literacy of prompt engineering [11]. This argument is supported by findings from studies. Based on research conducted at a Swiss university, it was demonstrated that both students and instructors must be trained to use AI tools responsibly [11]. There is a clear need to develop and implement institutional guidelines and to integrate AI-related competencies into educational programs.

Turning to the MOOC field, however, there is also a growing body of research. MOOC creators have begun using it to produce learning resources such as automated lecture summaries, video content, and interactive exercises [13]. For example, research by Sofyan [14] highlights how AI-driven interactive content can increase learner engagement. Another study by Yee et al. [15] examined the use of the technology can analyze the structure and sentiment of MOOC discussion forums, demonstrating how AI can automate content curation and identify common learning patterns. Nevertheless, concerns persist regarding trust in AI-generated educational materials, particularly when explanations and justifications are opaque, as noted by Swamy [16]. Consequently, explainable AI (XAI) is becoming a crucial focus area, as researchers seek to improve the transparency and interpretability of AI-generated content [17].

In summary, the reviewed contributions consistently emphasize the critical need to maintain human oversight in all stages of AI use in learning design and the production of learning resources, including MOOC-making. It seems that the research field warns that AI-generated learning content cannot be implemented directly without thorough human evaluation, editing, and validation. The prevailing consensus is that the use of AI for learning content development must be approached as a type of hybrid process that combines machine-generated content with human pedagogical judgment to ensure academic quality, ethical integrity, and pedagogical responsibility.

3 Methods

The data presented in this study is based on two surveys conducted among online students who attended two different SPOCs at a teacher training department at a university college. The students answered the same structured questionnaire, which included Likert-scale items and open-ended questions. Students' perceptions of AI-generated learning resources were operationalized through survey items measuring the perceived quality, usability, and learning outcomes associated with resources developed using generative AI. The first survey (fall 2023) received responses from 11 students (N=11) out of 25 who completed the course (44%), while the second survey (spring 2024) had 11 respondents (N=11) out of 22 (50%). Participation was voluntary, and all responses were anonymous. Following the methodological approach outlined by Ringdal [18], a basic statistical analysis was conducted, including frequency distributions, percentage analyses of responses, and a non-response analysis to assess data quality. Given the small sample size, simple design, and lack of validated instruments, the findings should be interpreted as preliminary and exploratory.

4 Data analysis

In the following data analysis, we first describe the learning design of the SPOCs and how the partially AI-generated learning resources were embedded, while the second part analyze the RQ: How do students perceive the use of AI-generated learning resources in SPOCs? This analysis is conducted in relation to specific survey items. Data from the first course is referred to as "SPOC1" while from the second as "SPOC2".

4.1 Learning design of the SPOCs and use of generative AI

The two SPOCs explored digital transformation in schools. The first course aimed to provide students—teachers working full-time in schools—with an understanding of schools as organizations and how organizational theory and technology implementation theory can be applied to analyze the consequences of digital transformation. The second course focused on digital change leadership, specifically how to implement and lead digital development projects within an educational context. Both courses followed an asynchronous learning design inspired by MOOC pedagogy and were structured into four modules, each addressing different aspects of digitalization. The learning design was largely consistent across both courses, following a structured learning pathway. This pathway typically began with an introduction to a theoretical concept, followed by activities designed to facilitate active learning. These activities included quizzes, discussion forums, and both minor and more extensive assignments.

However, generative AI was primarily used in the creation of different course content, including course text, images, reading guides, leading paragraphs, digital tests, assignments, and decorative elements. That said, it is imperative to emphasize that all AI-generated learning content was never used directly in the courses without educators enforcing strict quality control, implying always the presence of a "human in the loop".

Thus, all learning content underwent strict quality control by course creators before being implemented. Generative AI was part of a hybrid content development process, thus supporting SPOC-making rather than replacing human input. For example, a common approach involved course designers drafting an initial version of a course text, which was then refined with the assistance of generative AI. As a result, much of the content production was the outcome of a hybrid practice. Regarding the creation of digital tests, course instructors formulated prompts based on course content, allowing generative AI to generate draft assessments. These drafts were then reviewed and refined by subject matter experts to ensure academic rigor. Images were primarily generated using various generative AI tools and served mainly as decorative elements within the courses. AI-generated video content was rarely utilized, as the quality was insufficient, and production proved overly complex.

4.2 Student perception of AI-generated learning resources

Fig. 1. Students' use of learning resources SPOC1.

When students were asked about the types of learning resources they used to engage with course content, they were asked to evaluate these across four different modalities: illustrations, images, and diagrams; text in the LMS; videos; and attached articles and texts. The first two learning resources were largely generated using generative AI, whereas the remaining two were not. The analysis of student evaluations of these resources indicates that illustrations and videos were the least frequently used. For instance, in SPOC1, only 18.2% of students reported using illustrations, images, and diagrams to a large extent. In contrast, this percentage was higher in SPOC2, where 45.5% of students indicated a substantial reliance on visual materials. Text-based resources, particularly the AI-generated and edited learning resource "text in LMS," emerged as the most frequently utilized. In SPOC1, 54.5% of students reported a high

degree of engagement with text-based content, a trend that was similarly observed in SPOC2. These findings suggest that text-based learning resources were the most commonly used across both courses, whereas visual resources such as illustrations and videos were utilized to a much lesser extent. This highlights the continued preference for textual materials in asynchronous online learning environments.

Fig. 2. Students' use of learning resources SPOC2.

Fig. 3. Student perception of quality of learning resources SPOC1.

Students were asked to assess the quality of the learning resources. Overall, evaluations varied significantly. However, students generally perceived the learning resources as being of high quality and valuable to their learning process. The analysis indicates that text-based resources—whether produced by course instructors, extracted from books and scientific articles, or other textual materials—were rated as the most valuable. AI-supported texts available in the LMS were perceived as high-quality learning resources in both courses. For instance, in SPOC1, shown in Figure 3, 63.6% of students rated these AI-generated texts as very good, whereas in SPOC2, as shown in Figure 4, this figure was 27.3%. A notable discrepancy was observed between the two courses in the evaluation of illustrations, images, and diagrams. In SPOC1, 54.6% of students rated these visual resources as very good, while only 18.2% did so in SPOC2. The assessment of videos followed a similar pattern. Although videos were generally perceived as being of good quality in both courses, they consistently received lower ratings than text-based resources. Compared to other learning resources, videos were rated as less valuable in supporting students' learning processes.

Fig. 4. Student perception of quality of learning resources SPOC2.

Generative AI was extensively used to create digital tests in both courses and was considered a highly valued learning resource among students. In both SPOC1 and SPOC2, digital tests constituted a central component of the learning design, were evenly distributed, and each module included a substantial number of voluntary quizzes with automated formative feedback. Additionally, it was common for certain modules to conclude with a summative end-of-module test, based on the voluntary digital tests that students had worked with. Students were asked about their experiences using the

voluntary quizzes, which were largely generated with the assistance of AI. Each digital test was thematically linked to the course content that students had engaged with and typically consisted of between three and seven questions. The formative feedback was subject-specific, with a pedagogical focus on supporting students in learning key concepts within the discipline. To generate these tests, specific prompts were developed, instructing generative AI to formulate relevant question items along with corresponding formative feedback. These outputs were subsequently adapted to the different question formats used within the learning platform. The quizzes could, for example, consist of true/false questions, tasks requiring students to match concepts with corresponding answer options, or multiple-choice questions with one or more correct answers. Students were asked to evaluate the quizzes and their perceived learning outcomes by responding to a series of statements. These statements addressed whether the tests were challenging, whether the formative feedback contributed to their learning, the extent to which the tests helped them understand the course content, and whether the quizzes played a role in their overall learning experience. The data indicates that students were divided in their assessment of how effective the quizzes were for their learning. In SPOC1, shown in Figure 5, 63.6% of students disagreed with the statement that the tests were difficult, while in SPOC2, a larger proportion found them challenging. Regarding the perceived value of automated feedback, nearly three in ten students in SPOC1 considered it important for their learning, while in SPOC2, this proportion increased to four in ten. Furthermore, the findings suggest that students perceived the quizzes as contributing to their understanding of the subject matter. In SPOC1, nearly three in ten students strongly agreed that the digital tests enhanced their comprehension of the module content, whereas in SPOC2, this figure was two in ten. Overall, the findings indicate that digital tests provide valuable feedback and are perceived as a beneficial component of students' broader learning experience.

Fig. 5. Student perception of digital tests SPOC1.

5 Discussion and conclusion

This preliminary study examined students' perceptions of partially AI-generated learning resources in two SPOCs. Findings indicate that students generally value text-based partially AI-generated resources, as well as digital tests, although they emphasize that formative feedback mechanisms should be improved. Other modalities, such as AI-generated images, are perceived as less central to their learning. In this way, the study adds to and confirms the consensus outlined in the research horizon discussed earlier: students appreciate partially AI-generated learning resources, but such resources must always be safeguarded by educators to uphold pedagogical quality and ethical standards. An important consideration, however, is whether the course experience would differ without AI-generated resources. What would happen to the learning experience if generative AI were not used? This remains an open question requiring further research. However, it is the researchers' opinion that the absence of AI-generated resources would not significantly alter the learning experience, as the underlying goal would then be the production of high-quality course texts. Thus, generative AI does not fundamentally change the pedagogical approach or the learning outcomes; rather, its advantage lies in enhancing production efficiency. This highlights the need for further competence development in AI literacy and the emerging field of prompt engineering.

Addressing limitations, one shortcoming of this preliminary study is the very small sample size, meaning students' experiences may vary in different contexts. Further, the use of non-validated survey instruments limits the generalizability of the findings, and results should be interpreted as exploratory and indicative rather than definitive. Therefore, future studies should aim to include larger, more diverse samples and employ validated measures to strengthen the evidence base. Additionally, research could explore instructors' experiences with AI-assisted resource creation to provide a more comprehensive understanding of human-AI collaboration in SPOC-making. Nevertheless, it is likely that future teaching practices will continue to follow a hybrid approach, with AI acting as a support tool rather than an autonomous content creator.

Overall, this preliminary study underscores that while generative AI holds significant promises for supporting content creation in online education, its true value depends on careful human oversight, critical pedagogical judgment, and the responsible integration of emerging AI competencies.

6 References

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